

Synthesis and Characterization of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Ni(II) Ethylacetoacetate with Schiff Bases

O. P. ARORA* and SUDHINDRA N. MISRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 14 March 1980, revised 16 July 1980, accepted 7 August 1980

Some mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II) ethylacetoacetate with Schiff bases are synthesised and characterized by elemental analyses, magnetic, electronic and ir spectral studies. The results indicate that the complexes have near octahedral structure and the ligand is coordinated through nitrogen atom of azomethine group.

CONTINUED interest in the study of β -dicarbonyl complexes of nickel(II) appears to be mainly due to a variety of possible stereochemical configuration¹⁻³. Considerable attention has been paid to the Schiff base complexes of nickel(II)⁴⁻⁶, but not much work on the addition complexes of Schiff bases with β -dicarbonyl compounds of nickel(II) is reported. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to prepare and characterize the addition complexes of *bis*(ethylacetoacetato)nickel(II) with Schiff bases derived from the reaction of vanillin with diamine or α -naphthyl amine or thiosemicarbazide. Certain spectral parameters have also been reported which helped in assigning the possible stereochemistry.

Experimental

All chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as dimethylglyoximate after decomposing the complex with a mixture of $H_2SO_4-HNO_3$ and nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method. The elemental analyses of C and H were done by C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic moment measurements of the complexes in DMF were carried out on Gouy's magnetic balance at 300°K. The absorption spectra were taken in DMF on Carl-Zeiss VSU-2 spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} in KBr phase.

Schiff bases used were prepared by condensing vanillin with respective diamine or amine in stoichiometric quantities in ethanol and the Schiff bases obtained were recrystallized from ethanol and dried in vacuum at room temperature.

Preparation of complex [bis(ethylacetoacetato)(vanillin) ethylenediamine] Nickel(II): Diaquo-*bis*(ethylacetoacetato) Ni(II)⁷ (0.01M) was dissolved in benzene and to this Schiff base *bis*(vanillin) ethylenediamine (0.01M) in ethanol was added. No precipitation took place at room temperature. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. The volume of the green solution was reduced to one

third and the solution was left for crystallization in a desiccator for 3 to 4 days. The crystalline compound was washed several times with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of other complexes :

The reactions of diaquo-*bis*(ethylacetoacetato) Ni(II) with other Schiff bases were similarly carried out. In case of Schiff base *bis*(vanillin) thiosemicarbazone, the compound obtained was dirty brown viscous liquid. The product was washed several times with ether and kept in the desiccator for slow crystallization. It took about 7-8 days to isolate the crystalline compound. In case of Schiff base *bis*(vanillin) benzidine, precipitation took place on mixing the reactants at room temperature. The yellow precipitate obtained was washed with ethanol-ether mixture and dried *in vacuo*. All these compounds were found soluble in coordinating solvents like dimethylsulfoxide, dimethylformamide and pyridine. They are sparingly soluble in solvents like ethanol, methanol and benzene.

Results and Discussion

The observed and calculated analytical data show close resemblance within the experimental limits (Table 1). The magnetic moments (3.0 to 3.3 B.M.) of the complexes are within the normal octahedral range of nickel(II)^{8,9}, suggesting the presence of two unpaired electrons and hence the complexes are spin free with octahedral stereochemistry.

The observed spectral data and the ligand field parameters are given in Table 2. Three bands have been observed in each complex in the region 8810 to 8890 cm^{-1} , 13790 to 14180 cm^{-1} and 21510 to 23700 cm^{-1} . The ground state of octahedral d^8 system is A_{2g} and the above spin allowed transitions, assuming distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰ of the complexes, may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ in the order of increasing energy and are labelled as ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 respectively.

* Author for Correspondence.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA FOR SOME MIXED LIGAND Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Metal Complex	Physical state (Yield%)	%Ni Found (Calcd.)	%O Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	Melting point °C	Magnetic moment in Bohr Magneton μ_{eff}
1. Ni(E) ₂ (VB) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)	Yellow crystalline, (94)	7.2 (7.64)	62.8 (62.60)	5.3 (5.51)	3.1 (3.65)	300	3.902
2. Ni(E) ₂ (VP) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₈ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂)	Shining red crystalline, (85)	8.1 (8.46)	58.7 (58.89)	5.4 (5.52)	3.0 (4.04)	90.95	3.250
3. Ni(E) ₂ (VT) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S)	Dirty brown crystalline, (90)	8.6 (8.68)	51.0 (51.49)	5.1 (5.21)	5.9 (6.21)	90.0	3.288
4. Ni(E) ₂ (VD) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)	Brick red crystalline, (80)	8.4 (8.52)	55.1 (55.83)	5.9 (6.29)	5.8 (6.10)	250 (decomposes)	3.196
5. Ni(E) ₂ (VE) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂)	Dark brown crystalline, (93)	8.9 (9.09)	55.8 (55.88)	5.9 (5.98)	4.0 (4.38)	148	3.010
6. Ni(E) ₂ (VN)(H ₂ O) Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)(H ₂ O)	Green crystalline, (90)	8.9 (9.58)	58.2 (58.84)	5.5 (5.76)	2.1 (2.28)	115-120	3.127

E = ethylacetoacetato; VB = bis(vanillin)benzidine, VP = bis(vanillin)-o-phenylenediimine; VT = bis(vanillin)thiosemicarbazone; VD = bis(vanillin)diethylenetriamine, VE = bis(vanillin)ethylenediimine; VN = vanillin- α -naphthylimine.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC BANDS AND SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹)

Complexes*	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	B	β	ν_2/ν_1	ν_3/ν_1	ν_3/ν_2	f	h_x	CFSE in K.cal/mole
1. Ni(E) ₂ (VB)	8890	13790	21510	565.5	0.54	1.55	2.42	1.56	1.00	3.83	30.67
2. Ni(E) ₂ (VP)	8850	13890	21600	570.58	0.55	1.57	2.44	1.56	1.01	3.75	30.80
3. Ni(E) ₂ (VT)	8310	14080	23730	690.7	0.66	1.60	2.58	1.61	0.99	3.83	30.25
4. Ni(E) ₂ (VD)	8890	14180	23700	751.74	0.72	1.60	2.67	1.67	0.98	2.33	30.57
5. Ni(E) ₂ (VE)	8730	13980	22620	692.86	0.67	1.60	2.59	1.62	0.98	2.74	29.98
6. Ni(E) ₂ (VN)(H ₂ O)	8770	14290	23750	781.3	0.75	1.63	2.71	1.66	0.99	2.08	30.10

* The abbreviations used here are the same as used in Table 1.

TABLE 3—INFRARED DATA

Ni(E) ₂ (VE)	Ni(E) ₂ (VD)	Ni(E) ₂ (VP)	Ni(E) ₂ (VT)	Ni(E) ₂ (VB)	Ni(E) ₂ (VN)(H ₂ O)	Assignment (Frequency cm ⁻¹)
3300 sbr	3130 vw	3320 s	3350 s	3210 ms	3260 w	N-H stretching vibration
3210 s	3030 vw	3130 m	3260 ms	3140 s	3030 w	
1660 s	1650 sbr	1660 w	1665 s 1600 m	1665 s	1650 s	C=N stretching vibration
1585 m	1585 s	1590 s	1590 s	1585 s	1580 w	
1500 m	1500 s	1515 sbr	1490 s	1500 s	1500 s	Aromatic C=C vibration
1460 m	1460 w	1460 s	1460 w	1460 w	1465 m	
1430 sh	1430 w	1430 m	1425 w	1425 w	1430 m	
1265 w	1285 m	1280 vw 1265 s	1285 w 1260 s	1290 w 1265 s	1260 s	C-O stretching vibration
1230 w	1225 m	1220 w	1215 w	1225 w	1225 w	
1155 w	1150 w	1205 w	1170 vw	1210 w	1205 w	Aromatic in-plane deformation vibration
1120 s	1120 s	1150 w	1145 w	1170 m	1170 s	
1028 m	1025 m	1020 s	1120 w	1150 w	1150 w	
		1025 s	1020 s	1120 m	1120 m	
				1030 m	1090 m	
				1060 w _{me} 1020 w	1060 m 1020 m	
855 m	860 w	860 w	860 w	860 vw	855 m	-OH out-of-plane vibration
820 s	825 m	820 m	820 m	820	820 s	
780 m	780 w	780 m	780 w	780 s	780 m	Aromatic OH out-of-plane vibration
730 s	725 w	725 s	725 m	725 w	745 s 725 w	
435 m	455 vw	445 m	435 wbr	440 w	435 w	νNi-N

* The abbreviations used here are the same as used in Table 1.

For d⁸ complexes with O_h symmetry, Lever¹¹ observed that the configuration interaction between high spin T_{1g}(P) and T_{1g}(F) excited state lowers the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from the theoretical value of 1.8 to ~1.5-1.7 which is in confirmation with our experimental data supporting the distortion in

octahedral symmetry. The value of the ratios ν_2/ν_1 and ν_3/ν_2 are also found within the range of the octahedral stereochemistry.

Various numerical methods suggested by Konig¹² have been used to calculate the value of B (Racah parameter). The value of B obtained by

using modified Tanabe-Sugano diagram¹³ lies in close agreement with the above value.

The value of β (nephelauxetic ratio) shows a trend of covalent bonding in all the complexes. The CFSE values in all the complexes are almost the same which support the magnetic data. An inter-comparison of Dq and B values for the complexes shows that Dq increases in the sequence VN>VD>VT>VE>VP>VB in the spectrochemical series and almost in the inverse order in nephelauxetic series. The values of the crystal field parameter f is almost the same in all the complexes which may be due to no change in CFSE of the complexes. The nephelauxetic parameters for ligand varies from complex to complex which is due to substituted group in the ligand.

Infrared frequencies along with their tentative assignments are shown in Table 3. The band attributable to the intramolecular hydrogen bonded -OH has not disappeared in the complexes and phenolic C-O vibration shows negligible shift. This indicates that -OH of the ligand has not taken part in complex formation¹⁴. The elemental analysis supports the above statement. A strong band around 1590 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the C=N stretch of the free Schiff bases and that found in the region 1650-1670 cm⁻¹ for the complexes. This frequency shift suggests the coordination through azomethine nitrogen¹⁵.

Aromatic in-plane deformation vibration bands between 1275 and 960 cm⁻¹, =CH out-of-plane vibration band near 860 cm⁻¹ and aromatic CH out-of-plane vibration bands between 860 and 735 cm⁻¹¹⁶ in the ligand do not resemble the ir spectra of the complexes. This is another support for complex formation.

The characteristic bands due to the C=O and C=C group of the bis(ethylacetoacetato) nickel(II) are found at 1632 cm⁻¹ and 1527 cm⁻¹¹⁷ respectively. The former one shifts to higher frequencies whereas the latter one shifts to lower frequencies. The bands appearing in the region 1720-1450 cm⁻¹ on complexation, are difficult to assign as various bands fall in this region. However, the bands have been assigned tentatively comparing the spectra of the respective ligand.

Metal nitrogen stretching vibration also appears in the region 455-435 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes.

This band either does not shift or shifts slightly on complexation. Other Ni-N bands fall below the range of instrument.

Conclusion

The present paper describes the synthesis, magnetic and spectral study of high spin, near octahedral complexes of nickel(II) with Schiff bases. Emphasis is placed on calculation and accuracy of the interelectronic repulsion parameters. However, no quantum mechanical theory has been developed which would provide a quantitative basis for the nephelauxetic effect. It is believed that such attempts will not be successful until criteria on the accuracy and reliability of the parameter values determined from the spectra become available. To this end, the present paper is also an attempt like the other worker¹⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor and Prof. A. N. Nigam for their interest in the work.

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